

Early and Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy in Case of Acute Cholecystitis; an Observational Study in Tertiary Health Care**Abinasha Mohapatra¹, Kishan Bhoi², Ansuman Pradhan³, Himansu Shekhar Mishra⁴**¹Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, Fakir Mohan Medical College and Hospital, Balasore, Odisha, India, 756019²Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, Veer Surendra Sai Institute of Medical Science And Research (VIMSAR), Burla, Sambalpur, Odisha, India, 768017^{3,4}Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri, Odisha, India, 752002

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Corresponding Author: Himansu Shekhar Mishra

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Abstract:**Background:** The position of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis isn't always but sincerely set up. The aim of this prospective randomized have a look at became to evaluate the protection and feasibility of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis and to compare the consequences with behind schedule cholecystectomy.**Methods:** among January 2023 and January 2024, forty patients with a diagnosis of acute cholecystitis had been randomly assigned to early laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 24 h of admission (early organization, n = 20) or to preliminary conservative remedy accompanied via behind schedule laparoscopic cholecystectomy, 6 to twelve weeks later (delayed group, n = 20).**Results:** there was no significant difference within the conversion costs (early, 25% vs not on time, 25%), running instances (early, 104 min vs behind schedule, 93 min), postoperative analgesia necessities (early, 5.3 days vs delayed, 4.8 days), or postoperative headaches (early, 15% vs behind schedule, 20%). but, the early group had significantly greater blood loss (228 vs 114 ml) and shorter hospital live (four.1 vs 10.1 days).**Conclusions:** Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis is secure and possible, offering the additional benefit of a shorter sanatorium stay. It has to be offered to sufferers with acute cholecystitis, furnished the surgery is performed inside 72 to 96 h of the onset of symptoms.**Keywords:** Acute cholecystitis, Laparoscopic cholecystectomy.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the gold well known for the remedy of sufferers with symptomatic gallstones. However, the function of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in acute cholecystitis is not but hooked up. In the developmental degrees of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, acute cholecystitis changed into considered a contraindication for the process. With growing experience in laparoscopic surgical, some of centres have suggested on the usage of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis [3,11,15,16], suggesting that it's miles technically feasible and safe. However, the conversion rate is high. Numerous randomized research within the pre laparoscopic era had proven that early open cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis become higher than delayed open cholecystectomy in phrases of shorter health centre stay, but each had similar operative mortality and

morbidity [4,6,10,12,14]. Early surgical operation for acute cholecystitis had in view that won popularity within the late Eighties. A success laparoscopic cholecystectomy throughout the length of acute inflammation is associated with an early recovery and shorter sanatorium live. but, those benefits of early laparoscopic cholecystectomy can be offset by using the capability dangers of great complications [1, 5, 9] and an excessive conversion charge. Theoretically, preliminary conservative remedy with antibiotics observed by means of c program language period optional cholecystectomy 6 to eight weeks later, after acute inflammation has subsided, may bring about a more secure operation with much less conversion fees. The selection between the two strategies of treatment is difficult due to the fact the statistics prospectively evaluating them are sparse. Simplest potential randomized trials [7,8] were

pronounced up to now. Therefore, we undertook a potential randomized look at to examine early and behind schedule laparoscopic cholecystectomy within the remedy of acute cholecystitis.

Patient selection and study design

Approval of this observes was acquired from the clinic ethics committee. Between January 2023 and January 2024, forty patients with a prognosis of acute cholecystitis admitted to the branch of surgical treatment, had been protected inside the take a look at. The prognosis of acute cholecystitis become based on a mixture of clinical standards (acute proper upper quadrant tenderness, temperature exceeding 37.5 °C, and white blood cellular rely more than $10 \cdot 10^9/l$) and Ultrasonographic standards (thickened, oedematous distended gallbladder; wonderful sonographic Murphy's sign; presence of gallstones; and pericholecystic fluid collection). Sufferers with signs for greater than 96 h, preceding higher stomach surgery, coexisting commonplace bile duct stones, or significant scientific sickness rendering them unfit for laparoscopic surgical operation were excluded from the have a look at. Informed consent turned into received. Patients have been then randomized into either the "early" institution or the "behind schedule" institution. Randomization turned into finished by way of a laptop-generated numbers listing stored by way of a 3rd birthday celebration. Inside the early group, laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed inside 24 h of randomization, while in the delayed organization, conservative treatment with intravenous fluids and antibiotics consisting of ampicillin, gentamicin, and metronidazole turned into given. The sufferers who spoke back to conservative treatment underwent an optional laparoscopic cholecystectomy 6 to twelve weeks after the extreme episode had subsided. The sufferers who failed conservative treatment had been handled with emergency open cholecystectomy.

Surgical procedure

The operation was completed by using representative surgeons, and the surgery becomes accomplished with the patient below widespread anaesthesia using endotracheal intubation. Pneumoperitoneum turned into created by blind

puncture with a Veress needle via a supraumbilical incision. four laparoscopic ports had been used: two 10-mm ports (one umbilical 10-mm port for the optical gadget and one epigastric port for the dissector/suction tool) and 5-mm ports (one on the midclavicular line alongside the proper subcostal margin and one inside the proper flank). If important, Adhesion launch and publicity of Calot's triangle had been first undertaken. If essential, the gallbladder turned into emptied via a laterally inserted Veress needle to permit better grasping. The cystic pedicle was dissected to isolate the cystic duct and the artery one at a time. Each have been then clipped and divided. Intraoperative cholangiogram changed into no longer done. The gallbladder changed into dissected off its mattress with a monopolar cautery hook. At final touch of the surgical treatment, the gallbladder became placed in a retrieval bag and extracted via the epigastric incision, which changed into enlarged if vital. Hemostasis turned into completed in gallbladder bed, and after a radical saline lavage, a suction drain becomes positioned if clinically indicated and the incisions closed. While required, conversion to the open system was done via a proper subcostal incision.

Postoperative Evaluation

Postoperatively, the patients had been allowed oral consumption 6–12 h after surgery supplied, that they had no nausea or vomiting. The single dose of antibiotics becomes repeated. ache comfort become obtained by means of intramuscular diclofenac injection, which turned into changed to pill management as soon as patient changed into allowed orally. The patients were discharged once the drain became removed and the affected person changed into afebrile and taking nutrition orally have a look at parameters records had been amassed prospectively and protected patient demographics, operative findings, conversion to open cholecystectomy, motives for conversion, operating time, postoperative analgesic requirement, length of postoperative stay and overall medical institution stay (consisting of the admission at presentation and admission for next behind schedule surgical operation in the delayed institution) and postoperative headaches.

Table 1: Clinical data and laboratory results for the patients in the early and delayed groups at admission

Sl. No.		Early group (n=20)	Delayed group (n=20)
1.	Age (years)	41.5 ± 11.4	38.6 ± 11.4
2.	Sex (M:F)	3 : 17	5 : 15
3.	Previous lower abdominal surgery	4	4
4.	Previous biliary symptoms	3	2
5.	Duration of acute symptoms (hours)	35.1 ± 19.1	36.1 ± 24.7
6.	Duration of symptoms (> 3 days)	2	5
7.	Maximum temperature	99.7 ± 0.2	99.2 ± 0.1
8.	Total leucocyte count (> 11000/ml)	13	11

9.	Total bilirubin (mg%)	0.7 ± 0.13	0.6 ± 0.14
10.	AST (U/I)	40.7 ± 20	30.8 ± 14
11.	ALT (U/I)	35.3 ± 18	25.4 ± 13
12.	Alkaline Phosphatase (IU/I)	187 ± 68	153 ± 48

Table 2: Ultrasound findings for the patients

Sl. No.	Ultrasound findings	Early group (n=20)	Delayed group (n=20)
1.	Thickened edematous gall bladder	12 (60%)	11 (55%)
2.	Distended gall bladder	17 (85%)	15 (75%)
3.	Presence of gall stone	20 (100%)	20 (100%)
4.	USG Murphy's sign positive	11 (55%)	13 (65%)
5.	Pericholecystic fluid	03 (15%)	03 (15%)

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis become completed the use of paired t-test and chi-rectangular check. A p price much less than zero.05 become taken into consideration significant.

Results

All through the study period, a total 40 sufferers have been randomized: 20 sufferers in the early organization and 20 patients within the behind schedule group. The 2 businesses had been nicely matched in phrases of age and intercourse, as well as clinical and laboratory parameters (desk 1). No affected person within the delayed group required urgent surgery because of failure of conservative remedy or recurrent symptoms after discharge. Delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy turned into achieved at a median interval of 68 days (range, forty eight–one hundred forty days) after initial admission.

Ultrasonographic and operative findings

The ultrasonographic findings of the patients in the two groups were comparable, as shown in the Table 2.

Operative procedures and operating time

More modifications in the operation technique (Table 3) and a longer operation time were required in the early group than in the delayed group. The mean operating time was 104 min (range, 40–210min) in the early group and 93 min (range, 35–200 min) in delayed group. The difference in operation time was not statistically significant ($p = 0.433$). In the successful laparoscopic group, the mean operative time was 87 min in early group, compared with 80 min in delayed group ($p=0.671$). The average blood loss was 228 ml in the early group and 114 ml in the delayed group ($p = 0.006$). No patient in either group required blood transfusion.

Conversion to open surgery

Five patients (25%) in early group and five patients (25%) in delayed group underwent conversion to open surgery ($p = 0.540$). The main reasons for conversion in the early cases were technical, including one case each of unclear Calot's triangle anatomy, suspicion of bile duct injury, minor bile duct injury, and transection of gall-bladder at Hartman's pouch. The main reason for conversion in the delayed group involved dense adhesions around Calot's triangle and gallbladder, making dissection difficult.

Table 3: Modification of the operative technique

Sl. No.	Modification of the technique	Early group (n=20)	Delayed group (n=20)
1.	Gall bladder decompression	16 (80%)	01 (05%)
2.	Retrieval bag	07 (35%)	00 (00%)
3.	Subhepatic drain	16 (80%)	07 (35%)
4.	Use of a fifth port	02 (10%)	00 (00%)
5.	Enlargement of the epigastric port site	01 (05%)	01 (05%)

Table 4: Operative complications observed

Sl. No.	Complications	Early group (n=20)	Delayed group (n=20)
1.	Intra-operative Complications		
	Bile duct injury	01	00
	Transection of Hartmann's pouch	01	00
2.	Post-operative Complications		
	Major bile leak	01	00
	Ileus	00	01
	Wound infection	01	02
	Total	04 (20%)	03 (15%)

Complications

There was no death in either group. The overall complication rate was 20% (4 of 20) in early group and 15% (3 of 20) in the delayed group. There was no major bile duct injury in the delayed group. However, in the early group one patient experienced postoperative cholangitis with subsequent cystic duct stump leak, which was treated by endoscopic retrograde cholangiography and stent placement. Another patient had a minor bile duct injury at the junction of the cystic duct with the bile duct. This required conversion and suturing of pinhole rent in the bile duct with a single 4-0 Vicryl stitch. In the delayed group, there were two wound infections and a postoperative ileus in one patient, which responded to conservative treatment (Table 4).

Post-operative analgesia requirement

The mean duration of postoperative analgesic requirement was 5.3 days in the early group and 4.8 days in the delayed group. Hospital stays The mean total hospital stay was 4.1 days (range, 2–20 days) in the early group and 10.1 days (range, 5–23 days) in the delayed group ($p = 0.023$). However, the mean postoperative hospital stay was 3.2 days (range, 1–20 days) in the early group and 2.3 days (range, 1–7 days) in the delayed group ($p=0.952$). The overall comparison of the patients in the early and delayed groups is shown in Table 5.

Discussion

In the early years of laparoscopic surgical procedure, acute cholecystitis was taken into consideration a relative contraindication to laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Currently, it has been shown that laparoscopic cholecystectomy is viable and safe for acute cholecystitis. Numerous studies have reported excessive conversion costs, ranging from 6% to 35% [2,3,11,13,15,16] for early laparoscopic cholecystectomy used to control acute cholecystitis. The better conversion rate obviates the advantages of early laparoscopic cholecystectomy. It is therefore argued that if not

on time laparoscopic cholecystectomy results in a technically simpler surgical treatment with a decrease conversion fee, it may be a better remedy option for acute cholecystitis. The general notion that initial conservative treatment will increase the risk of a hit laparoscopic cholecystectomy at a later date in all likelihood is not proper, as borne out by this take a look at. In our look at, each the early and not on time corporations had similar conversion prices.

The motives for conversion, but, were different. Within the early institution, the friable and edematous gall bladder tore whilst grasped. Furthermore, there was immoderate oozing as a result of acute inflammation. Inside the early degrees, we found these problems difficult to handle.

Except in one case, the Calot's triangle anatomy became fairly clean. as a consequence, inside the early organization, the con- model price showed a reducing fashion with enjoy (60% inside the first 5 cases to 13% in the remaining 15 instances). But, in delayed group, the main cause for conversion worried dense adhesions obscuring the anatomy of Calot's triangle. Even though our 25% conversion price seems to be excessive, it reflects our protection worries for the method, and we consider that extra revel in with early surgical procedure for those cases may carry the conversion fee down.

Our enjoy supports the notion that the inflammation related to acute cholecystitis creates an edematous aircraft across the gallbladder, as a consequence facilitating its dissection from the encompassing structures. Watching for the inflamed gallbladder to quiet down lets in maturation of the surrounding inflammation and consequences in agency of the adhesions, main to scarring and contraction, which make the dissection more difficult. additionally, although inflammation in early levels may not always contain Calot's triangle, chronic inflammation often scars and distorts Calot's triangle, making dissection on this important location more difficult.

Table 5: Overall comparison of early and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy groups

Sl. No.		Early group (n=20)	Delayed group (n=20)
1.	Age (years)	41.5 ± 11.4	38.6 ± 11.4
2.	Sex (M:F)	3 : 17	5 : 15
3.	Duration of symptoms (hours)	35.1 ± 19.1	36.1 ± 24.7
4.	Opening time (minutes)	104.3 ± 44	93 ± 45
5.	Blood loss (ml)	228.5 ± 142	114.5 ± 99
6.	Post-operative stay (days)	3.2 ± 8	2.3 ± 2
7.	Total hospital stay (days)	4.1 ± 8.6	10.1 ± 6.1
8.	Post-operative analgesia (days)	5.3 ± 1.4	4.8 ± 0.7
9.	Conversion rate	25%	25%
10.	Complications	4 (20%)	03 (15 %)

The distinction inside the operation instances turned into no longer significant, although early group sufferers required a longer operation time than the delayed group. However, the overall health center live inside the behind schedule institution, which included the total time spent for the duration of admissions, was significantly longer than inside the early institution.

Conclusion

Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy is possible and secure for acute cholecystitis. We consider that growing revel in should bring down the difficulty fee in the early institution. Not on time laparoscopic cholecystectomy is not associated with a lower conversion rate than that associated with early laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Early laparoscopic surgical operation offers definitive remedy on the initial admission and avoids the troubles of failed conservative control and recurrent symptoms, which require emergency surgery. further- extra, early surgical procedure is associated with a much shorter hospital live, that is a prime monetary benefit to each the affected person and health care device.

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